

MARINE INFORMATION SERVICE: AN INTEGRAL APPROACH

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Abstract

This paper describes the design and operation of a regional service office in Alaska. A new approach is presented for joint federal and state participation in a user-funded facility. Case studies emphasize the benefits of the design and operation. Transfer of this expertise is outlined in the concluding remarks.

1. Executive Summary

The course for the future in regional service delivery is shaped by the needs of the user and the distribution of capabilities. The right assets in the right place will require careful examination of how the dynamics operate. An integral concept which incorporates the best parts from separate entities has an advantage in tomorrow's service-oriented world. Responding to the demands of the regional users, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) has established field offices under the National Satellite Data and Information Service (NESDIS), and in Anchorage the field office is located within the office space of the University of Alaska's Arctic Environmental Information and Data Center. Joint projects have been successfully completed which have nurtured the integral approach. Direct support of regional users has driven the development of data input, control, analysis, and product capabilities. Concurrently, the NOAA field offices represent all centers within NESDIS for distribution of products and for receipt of requests to the national information centers. On the regional scale, an integral approach allows the best attributes from each organization to be utilized in serving the public, commercial companies, private industry, state and local agencies, and regional projects under federal management. The model for expanding the regional capabilities is an integral one, and it would be directly applicable to plans by NOAA to implement Regional Ocean Service Centers in the near future.

2. Introduction

The operational concepts have crystallized from experiences in service delivery from 1975 when the National Oceanographic Data Center (NODC) of NOAA created the Anchorage field office. NODC

is one of four centers within NESDIS of NOAA, and the Anchorage field office is located within the office space of the University of Alaska. An interagency agreement between the two organizations (NOAA and the University) has been the foundation of joint projects in Alaska. The integral approach includes the operation of a regional office in Anchorage which is staffed by each organization, both state and federal. The integral approach corresponds to the types of services which span the range of activities from input to products. Lastly, the integral approach embraces the NOAA mission of information exchange in the NESDIS liaison operations where separate scientific disciplines are focused through the field officers.

The design for the future is molded by the triumphs of the past. Several projects have been completed as others continue, and during these projects, new solutions to problems were developed. Because the process of development has been evolving in direct response to user requirements, the integral approach receives timely information on the needs within the region. As conditions change, the energies can be redirected as the situation demands. Weak areas can be strengthened; critical deadlines can be met; unusual, unique concerns can be addressed. Because the needs change, the operation must be flexible. New expertise has been added to the regional capability when a project terminates. Therefore, the integral approach incorporates a legacy of success as building blocks for the future.

The second attribute of the approach is that home organizations provide the foundation--the fundamental mission--but the operations are directed to sponsoring projects which provide the funding. Because the regional office must survive on contractual relationships with third-party organizations, the performance of the services is essential in sustaining funds. At the same time, the contracts must fall within the basic missions of the home organizations. This process assures that services offered match the needs and funding of those organizations which require the services. The integral approach relies on self-sufficiency and the dynamics of supply and demand. The relationship of sponsors, home organizations, and the regional office forms a network among all three components. The bonds between home organization and the regional office are the basic missions of

the home organizations. The bonds between the sponsoring organizations and the regional office are contractual commitments. The regional office becomes a pathway through which the home organizations interact with third-party organizations. Bonds replace direct-line authority and contracts replace directly appropriated funding.

Because the resources are located in the region, assets are near the users. These assets are designed to meet the intrinsic requirements of the contracts and to augment the established capability of the home organizations. Communications with NODC are supported by several pathways. Voice phone lines link staff directly in both locations. Terminals allow messages to be transmitted among the field offices and the central office. Data bases at NODC can be searched remotely from the field offices. When information is gathered in the region, it can be transmitted either directly by electronic equipment or mailed on the media processed by the regional office. Linking the regional office to the central office with multiple paths minimizes one potential concern.

Another aspect of the design is compatibility within the regional office and with both the user and the home organization. As a result, the proper assets are located in the region. These assets are balanced with the needs of the user and the technical abilities of the regional staff. If the equipment does not achieve the needs, then it is not appropriate. If the staff cannot operate it, then it is useless. A basic requirement for service is inputting new data. Data entry devices have been installed, and staff have been selected and trained to support this need. Another requirement is checking data received from third parties that will be forwarded to the central office. Data with errors are not valuable commodities for either the submitter or the receiver. Checking requires a data control capability within the region. Equipment which can check and correct errors has been installed, and specialized computer programs have been implemented on the checking equipment.

Displaying the information in useful forms is another requirement, and specialized programs have been written. Computer-generated graphs are another form of useful display. A graphic terminal subsystem has been installed, and business-styled graphs can be created for reports, presentations, and preliminary assessments. Map-based products have always been highly prized by the users.

Connecting this capability to the central office and to the user is another requirement. Interfaces and terminal networking have been implemented on equipment in the region. Word processors have been interfaced to microcomputers. Graphic terminals have been connected to a microcomputer acting as a regional node in the network. User terminals can be connected via telephone lines with asynchronous modems.

To summarize the generic requirements of the regional office, equipment must be selected which

meets the objectives and can be operated efficiently by the regional staff. The tasks for the equipment are data capture, data checking, data display, and data communications. Blending these requirements into an operational configuration is a continuing job. There are shifts among the tasks because, in time, the work load moves from one task to another. The integral approach is well suited to this operational environment.

3. Operational Method

The four fundamental requirements for the regional office are executed by a combination of trained staff, proper equipment, and strong management. The composition of staff and equipment has changed as the dominant requirements changed. In the early years, data capture dominated, and data entry equipment was operated by keyentry operators. As data control requirements grew, a shift to checking equipment was initiated. Programming capability was developed from within the existing staff and from recruitment outside the organization. Computer graphics were added, and operators were trained from the home organization in the region. Telecommunications became significant, and communication interfaces were installed as the staff became proficient in terminal operations and networking. Training and system development were integrated into a comprehensive design. Considerations were given to operational concerns during the development stages. As a result, new capabilities were merged with existing operations with minimal disruption or start-up time.

It is important that skills among the staff overlap other members so that more energies can be directed to a single task. Each member is assigned a principal area of activity with secondary responsibilities. Even the project manager has data operations and programming tasks within the secondary level. Everyone can be utilized if production of the workload demands it. The goal is to have the staff skills span the full range of capabilities and to eliminate any gaps in expertise within the spectrum. Intrinsic to the operations is that the equipment has more than one operator assigned and the devices themselves have redundant capabilities. As the workload changes, the configuration is transformed to support the requirement.

From this foundation, the four requirements are maintained by a staff consisting of a project manager, a computer programmer, a data control clerk, a secretary, and a graphics terminal operator. The relationship is divided into three levels given in the figure below.

This structure provides the proper oversight and allows augmentation or exchange of capabilities at a later date. By training or recruiting from within the staff, the investment in previous training is preserved. Concurrent projects can be supported by adding staff or transferring resources.

Because the equipment is balanced with the staff and contractual commitments, the components must be compatible in two forms. The media must be exchangeable among the separate subsystems, or the subsystems must be connected directly through cables and interfaces. This design gives the project manager many options in operating the system and addresses two basic concerns. One concern is equipment contention, where many people want one device simultaneously. The second concern is lost time due to equipment repair or maintenance. Intrinsic redundancy in capability addresses both of these concerns.

The four requirements combined with the staff structure and equipment configuration map into a series of specific operational tasks. Table 1 below identifies the tasks and equipment components for the task.

These tasks require specialized computer programs, and the operators must develop supporting manuals as required. Over four hundred checking programs have been written and maintained on the Wang equipment. Graphics software has been purchased from the open market, and map-based displays have been developed internally. User manuals have been developed for the graphic services and the data entry services, and these manuals have been distributed to the user organizations.

The components in the configuration have primary and secondary operators. Because the tasks defined in Table 1 meet the four basic requirements, the operators can select alternate paths for the same tasks. Table 2 below links the equipment and operators to the primary and secondary functions for each component.

With the redundancy incorporated in the design, the staff has several methods to complete the tasks. Because several staff members can exchange skills on the redundant devices, operational flexibility is an important element in the integral approach.

4. Case Studies

This flexibility has been utilized for the sponsoring organizations under contract since 1976-77. To date, five sponsors have initiated projects for these services. The federally funded projects include NOAA and the Department of Interior's Minerals Management Service (MMS). For NOAA, the sponsors are the Ocean Pollution Data and Information Network (OPDIN), the Marine Ecosystems Analysis Project--Puget Sound, the Brine Disposal Program, and the Outer Continental Shelf Environmental Assessment Program (OCSEAP) for Alaska. The MMS office in Alaska has worked through the OCSEA Program for environmental research in the Alaska coastal waters. From each sponsor, one or two examples will be presented as case studies.

OPDIN has sponsored a special study of marine data entry. Because the OPDIN managers have identified a significant volume of manuscript-format data, the first concern was the to capture data from the paper forms. A 2½-year study was completed that measured the productivity factors by type of operator, type of entry device, and style of original material. Three operators were selected for the list: a keyentry operator, a secretary, and a scientific technician. Dedicated entry devices were tested, terminals were used with telephone lines, microcomputers were included, and emerging technologies were evaluated. Twenty-two data sets were delivered by the sponsor, to be used by each operator. A matrix of results was obtained for each operator which recorded the time required to complete each step in the entry process. These results were normalized to remove the effect of size. A final report was prepared for the sponsor, and a summary was given last year at the Oceans'83 conference.

The data entry project involved the entry and checking capabilities because the error rates were monitored for each operator. Computer programming was required for the microcomputer system and voice entry subsystem. System design and procurement dominated the early phases of the project, and testing and analyses dominated the later phases. A secretarial operator was recruited for the project on a temporary appointment. Except for the graphics terminal operator, all other staff members participated at some time during the project.

The second sponsor is the MMS office, and two projects were coordinated simultaneously. Because the MMS office had funded whale survey studies, they wanted results from the surveys as soon as possible. A telecommunication link between the North Slope of Alaska and Anchorage was used to transmit flight and sighting information. These results were converted to map products and delivered to the local MMS office. Near-real-time information was available to the sponsor. The other project centered on the production of business graphs for internal documents and analyses. Pie charts, Bar charts, Gantt charts, and linear diagrams were generated from management and scientific information. Rapid turn-around times were essential in meeting the deadlines.

The staff for these two projects included primarily the graphic terminal operator with assistance from the programmer and data control clerk. The microcomputer (HP 1000 Model 6) was the interface between the North Slope and Anchorage. The graphics terminal generated the whale survey maps and business graphs.

The third sponsor, Marine Ecosystems Analysis Project--Puget Sound, required data control for several types of biological data. In particular, the intertidal data sets from two contractors were checked, edited, and final-processed. Multiple subsets from a single survey period were merged, and duplicate records were removed. Missing values were added to existing records. Errors were corrected in the digital and taxonomic code fields plus the parametric fields. Data sets were re-sequenced by record number during the control process. Statistical information was extracted from the files and confirmed by the original contractor as valid information. New checking programs were installed to isolate areas of concern. Over one hundred data sets were final-processed. Production work centered on the data control clerk, programmer, and project manager using the Wang and IBM equipment.

Parallel activities were executed for the fourth sponsor, the Brine Disposal Project. Fishery data sets had been received in a format designed in the late 1970's. When the data base changed the format to a new and improved style, the earlier data sets had to be converted to the new style. A careful review of the old formats was the first task, and the coding of the earlier data sets demanded additional changes before conversion. A special conversion scheme was installed on the computer equipment which eliminated

many errors during the conversion process. Problems with taxonomic entries were corrected after the records had been transformed to the new style. After conversion, the new data sets were final-processed by checking the data sets with the computer programs. A combined effort by the programmer and data control clerk assured a timely and accurate execution of the various steps.

The last sponsor, the OCSEA Program, was the first major supporter and has continued to request special projects since 1977. All regional capabilities have been employed to address the continuing activities of this major research managing organization. Because the scope of work has remained significant, the OCSEA Program uses the data entry, data checking, data product, and data communication capabilities of the regional office. A special relationship exists between the OCSEA Program and the NODC because the data base for Alaska research is maintained at NODC. To assure the quality of the data base, data base requirements have been incorporated into the regional checking procedure. Special management support files have been developed at the request of OCSEAP management. A logical focus for these two requirements is the regional office.

The data entry capability expedites delivery of data sets to the data base and provides a mechanism to underwrite program commitments for deliverables from research contracts. The checking capability ensures that accurate information is submitted to the data base. Data products support the scientific advancement of the program. Telecommunications have linked distant elements effectively and in a timely manner. All staff members have participated in projects sponsored by OCSEAP, and all components have been utilized as required. Temporary augmentation of existing resources has been implemented by the regional office. Assets and staff from the home organization have been directed to this augmentation and released when the task was completed.

5. Summary

The power of the integral method has been demonstrated and continues today from the successes of the past. The continuation of the regional office depends on satisfied customers. Yearly installments of funding have only been received because the projects were completed on time and within the budget. The five sponsoring organizations have maintained contact with the regional center on a continuing basis. Even though the sponsors only see the end results, those results are directly linked to the integral method. The dynamics of service delivery change with time, and the integral method is best adapted to a changing environment. The best parts from the home organizations are located where the users are. The intrinsic flexibility and alternate pathways allow a rapid response to new commitments. Temporary adjustments can be made to the staff and equipment in a short lead time. Operating in this manner, the process is very energetic and active.

Gaining this expertise and exploring this method is not the principal objective. The important goal is transferring this knowledge and expertise to others. Not only is this transfer a federal mandate, but also the value to others can be multiplied with each transfer.

This conference and proceedings are important vehicles in technology transfer and valuable opportunities to disseminate the information. The timeliness of the conference coincides with major plans by NOAA to develop Region Ocean Service Centers. Transferring this expertise to the NOAA plan would be very rewarding and an important

contribution to the success of the centers. Concurrently, the Alaska regional office will develop new capabilities in response to the demands of the sponsoring organizations. Local seminars will be scheduled, and interested parties will be invited to share in the developments. Technology transfer will be an important goal, and the principal beneficiaries will be the home organizations that provide the foundation for the regional office. NOAA's National Oceanographic Data Center and the University of Alaska have separate and mutual missions which are satisfied in part by the operation of the regional office.

Table 1

OPERATIONAL TASKS

<u>Definition</u>	<u>Equipment</u>
TERMINAL TELECOMMUNICATIONS FOR MESSAGE TRANSFER, ELECTRONIC MAIL, ETC.	TI 745 terminal HP 2647F terminal
TELECOMMUNICATION NODE FOR THE OCEAN POLLUTION DATA AND INFORMATION NETWORK (OPDIN)	HP 1000 Model 6 microcomputer
GRAPHIC PRODUCTS FOR MANAGEMENT APPLICATIONS: Business graphs Map-based displays	HP 2647F graphics terminal
DATA BASE SUPPORT BY PRE-PROCESSING DATA SUBMISSIONS: Taxonomic code conversion Format conversion Data checking and editing	Wang 2200VP minicomputer
DATA REDUCTION: Tables, summaries, etc.	Wang 2200VP minicomputer
DATA ENTRY SERVICES TO CAPTURE DATA FROM MANUSCRIPTS TO DIGITAL FORMAT: Keyentry Voice entry	IBM 3741 workstation Lear Siegler ADM5 terminal with voice board
WORD PROCESSING INTERFACED TO DATA PROCESSING: Access to typesetting via Displaywriter network	IBM Displaywriter
DISTRIBUTION OF REFERENCE MATERIAL IN DIGITAL FORMAT: Master files of taxonomic codes	Wang 2200VP minicomputer

Table 2

EQUIPMENT UTILIZATION

<u>Device</u>	<u>Operator</u>	<u>Primary Function</u>	<u>Secondary Function</u>
IBM 3741 WORKSTATION	Data control clerk	Data entry Data update	Printing
WANG 2200VP MINI- COMPUTER	Data control clerk Programmer	Data checking Printing Analyses	Data entry Data update
HP 2647F GRAPHICS TERMINAL	Graphics operator Project manager Programmer	Business graphs Map-based displays	Telecommunication access
TI 745 TERMINAL	Project manager Secretary	Telecommunication access	Data entry
HP 1000 MODEL 6 MICROCOMPUTER WITH CONSOLE AND LEAR SIEGLER ADM5 VOICE TERMINAL	Programmer Data control clerk	Computation File transfer Word processing interface Printing	Telecommunication access Graphics Data entry Data update
DISPLAYWRITER	Secretary	Text preparation Typesetting interface Letter-quality printing	Telecommunication access